

Formation of Heterocyclic Compounds. Part VI. Synthesis of Tetrahydroacridones.

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In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 309), it was shown that by boiling a mixture of ethyl *cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate* (I) and an arylamine for a few minutes, *cyclohexanone-2-carbanilide* (II) is produced, which in its turn on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid on the water-bath, may be easily converted into a tetrahydrophenanthridone derivative (III). It was also pointed out in that communication that by conducting the same reaction at the ordinary temperature, an anil (IV) could be readily obtained. This has been now fully realised as several primary aromatic amines have been condensed with ethyl *cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate* and the reaction product have been further induced to undergo an intramolecular condensation to give rise to different tetrahydroacridone derivatives (V).*

* Although published in May, 1929, there is no reference to this communication in a paper communicated by Blount, Perkin and Plant on the 29th June, 1929, and published in the *Journal of London Chemical Society*, in September, 1929. This oversight might have been due to the latter authors not having noticed our aforesaid communication.

Aniline, *p*-toluidine, and *m*-xylydine readily react with ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate at the room temperature to give rise to different anils and these on being heated for a short time at 260-265° yielded the corresponding tetrahydroacridone derivatives. It is only in the former case that the anil was obtained in a pure state, but other anils remained as a reddish-brown oil which resisted all attempts to solidify them. *p*-Aminoacetanilide also yields an anil, ethyl 2-*p*-acetaminoanilidocyclohexane-1-carboxylate, but this cannot be induced to undergo intramolecular condensation either by heating or by the action of concentrated sulphuric acid. The sulphuric acid solution on dilution gives diazo-reaction and the non-formation of any acridone derivative may be accounted for by the presence of the anil (VI) in the form of an ion (VII) in concentrated sulphuric acid solution (*cf.* Roberts and Turner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, p. 1932). The ease of all such condensations appears to be affected mostly by the basicity of the amine used, for no nitraniline, or β -naphthylamine could be made to condense with the ester.

Kötz and Merkel (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1909, 79, 122) obtained ethyl 2-anilido- $\Delta^{1:2}$ -cyclohexene-1-carboxylate (IV) by heating a mixture of ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate with aniline and keeping the product for several days. But it has already been shown (Sen and

Basu, *loc. cit.*) that this kind of reaction gives rise to *cyclohexanone*-2-carbanilide (m.p. 105°) (II). That the Kötze and Merkel's compound is an anil is further evident from the fact that it readily yields 1:2:3:4-tetrahydroacridone (V), the constitution of which is known as it can be synthesised by heating a mixture of *cyclohexanone* and anthranilic acid (Tiedtke, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 631).

All the tetrahydroacridone derivatives described in this paper are well crystalline solids of high melting points. They are soluble in most organic solvents and are more basic than their isomeric tetrahydrophenanthridone derivatives as they easily dissolve even in dilute acids.

It is curious to note that whilst (II), (IV), (VIII) and (IX)—the two latter obtained by the action of aniline on 2-acetyl*cyclohexanone* (Borsche, *Annalen*, 1910, 317, 70), can be readily dehydrated to yield ring-compounds, the analogous compound (Xa or Xb) obtained by the action of aniline on 2-hydroxymethylene*cyclohexanone* cannot be induced to undergo an intramolecular condensation. This behaviour of 2-hydroxymethylene*cyclohexanone* derivative also suggest that its constitution would be best represented by (Xa) as previously mentioned (Sen and Basu, *loc. cit.*).

Inactivity of this compound led us to study the action of ammonia on 2-hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone*. The amide (m.p. 112°) obtained by the action of liquor ammonia on 2-hydroxymethylene*cyclohexanone* readily reacts with excess of hydroxylamine hydrochloride to give rise to the oxime of 2-cyanocyclohexanone evidently by the intermediate formation of the isoxazole derivative (Auwers, Bohr and Fresse, *Annalen*, 1925, 414, 66). The amide also reacts with cyanoacetamide to give rise to the quinoline derivative (XI, Sen-Gupta *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1351).

(Xa)

(Xb)

which in its turn can be hydrolysed with concentrated sulphuric acid to the acid (XII).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate and Aniline.: (i) *Formation of Ethyl 2-Anilido- Δ^1 -cyclohexene-1-carboxylate (IV).*—Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (4 g.) and aniline (2.2 g.) were mixed together in a small flask and left overnight in vacuum over fused calcium chloride. After three days fine crystals began to separate and in a week the contents in the flask set in to a crystalline solid (yield, 5 g.), which was collected and dried over porous plate. (Found: N, 5.91. $C_{15}H_{19}O_2N$ requires N, 5.71 per cent.).

The substance crystallises from methyl alcohol in very light yellow prisms and melts at 58.5° . It is soluble in ether, alcohol, and even in petroleum ether in which the corresponding anilide (*cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-anilide*, m.p. $104-105^\circ$) is insoluble. A mixture of these two compounds melts at 54° . The anil does not give any colouration to an alcoholic solution of ferric chloride. It is similar to that described by Kötze and Merkel (*loc. cit.*) who however records a melting point at 29° .

(ii) *Formation of 1: 2: 3: 4-Tetrahydroacridone.*—The above anil was heated in an oil-bath at 260° for a few minutes when diphenylcarbamide (m.p. $233-235^\circ$) sublimed off and condensed in the air condenser and the receiver, while the liquid in the flask was soon transformed into a fine crystalline solid. This was collected, washed with ether and cold alcohol and was finally crystallised from ethyl alcohol. (Found: N, 7.2. $C_{13}H_{13}ON$ requires N, 7.04 per cent.). It melted at $357-358^\circ$ and was identified as 1: 2: 3: 4-tetrahydroacridone by direct comparison with an authentic specimen prepared by heating anthranilic acid with cyclohexanone according to the method

of Tiedtke (*loc. cit.*), which after two crystallisations from ethyl alcohol melted at 358°. A mixture of this and our compound also melted at the same temperature. The substance is soluble in dilute mineral acids and acetic acid.

Ethyl cycloHexanone-2-carboxylate and p-Toluidine: (i) *Formation of Ethyl 2-p-Methylanilido- Δ^1 -cyclohexene-1-carboxylate*.—Molecular proportions of the ketonic ester and *p*-toluidine were mixed together and left overnight. Next day the mixture was found to be turbid owing to the separation of water. The flask was then left in a vacuum over fused calcium chloride. But even after a month it was not possible to isolate any solid product from the reaction mixture.

(ii) *Formation of 7-Methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroacridone*.—The above dark liquid was heated in an oil-bath, the temperature of which was slowly raised to 265° and kept at that temperature for a few minutes when the di-*p*-tolylcarbamide (m.p. 260°) sublimed off. The residual solid found in the flask was collected, washed with ether and crystallised from alcohol. After recrystallising from the same solvent it melted at 340°. It was also soluble in dilute acids. (Found: N, 6.68. $C_{14}H_{15}ON$ requires N, 6.57 per cent.)

Ethyl cycloHexanone-2-carboxylate and m-Xylidine (asymmetric): *Formation of 7:9-Dimethyl-1:2:3:4-Tetrahydroacridone*.—A mixture of the ester (4.5 g.) and the xylidine (3.2 g.) was left in *vacuo* over fused calcium chloride. In this case also neither any crystal separated out nor any solid product was isolated. The red solution obtained, after the reaction was complete, was heated in an oil-bath at 260–265° for about 15 minutes when a liquid of *cyclo*ketonic smell and a crystalline solid were collected in the receiver. The crystals thus distilled off, were collected and washed with ether when it melted at 261–263°, which was not depressed by admixture with pure di-*m*-xylylcarbamide.

The contents in the flask set to a crystalline solid which was washed with ether and collected (yield, 4 g.). The substance crystallises from ethyl alcohol in small crystals melting at 316–318°. As usual it was also soluble in dilute mineral acids.

Ethyl cycloHexanone-2-carboxylate and p-Aminoacetanilide: *Formation of Ethyl 2-p-Acetamine-anilido- Δ^1 -cyclohexene-1-carboxylate (Formula VI)*.—The β -ketonic ester (2 g.) and the amine (1.8 g.) were dissolved in 10 c.c. glacial acetic acid and the solution

was warmed on a water-bath at 60° for 6 hours and then left overnight at the room temperature. Next morning the crystals (1·8 g.) separated were filtered, washed with dilute acetic acid, with cold dilute alcohol and finally with petroleum ether. (Found: N, 9·4. $C_{17}H_{23}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9·27 per cent.).

This anil crystallises from ethyl alcohol in small glistening flakes with a light yellow tinge. It melts at 191·5°; its alcoholic solution does not impart any colouration to ferric chloride. The substance decomposes on heating; so it was not possible to convert it into a tetrahydroacridone derivative by this method. Next it was heated on a steam-bath with concentrated sulphuric acid for over half an hour. No solid product of any definite constitution was isolated after the subsequent treatment of the reacted mixture, whereas the acid solution was found to contain the mother ester and a primary amine salt as it readily underwent diazotization.

Action of Ammonia on 2-Hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone.—Freshly distilled hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone was shaken with a considerable volume of liquor ammonia in a stoppered bottle and the reaction mixture was left overnight. Next morning a moderate quantity of a yellow solid product separated. The substance crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether and melted at 112°. (Found: N, 11·52. $C_7H_{11}ON$ requires N, 11·2 per cent.).

It is soluble in most organic solvents and in dilute acids, and it gives no sharp colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. When it is boiled with alkali, ammonia escapes and a red liquid is obtained which smells like hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone and also gives the characteristic colour reaction with ferric chloride in alcoholic solution.

Action of Hydroxylamine on the Amide.—An alcoholic solution of the compound was treated with sufficient hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of *excess* caustic soda solution, and the mixture was warmed for about 2 or 3 hours on a water-bath at 50-60° and then left overnight. Next day the solution was shaken with ether. The ethereal solution was allowed to evaporate after drying, when the compound began to separate in beautiful long needles. On crystallisation from alcohol it melted at 118°. It is supposed to be the oxime of 2-cyanocyclohexanone whose melting point as recorded by Auwers, Bahr and Fresse (*loc. cit.*) is 117-118°. It is most likely, that the excess of alkali hydrolyses the amide to the original hydroxymethyleneketone

which then reacts with hydroxylamine and gives rise to the cyanoketone in the usual way.

Condensation with Cyanoacetamide.—An intimate mixture of cyanoacetamide (1 mol.) and the above compound (1 mol.) was heated together in an oil-bath for about 10-15 minutes at 130-140° when ammonia was given off and the contents in the flask set to a crystalline mass. This was collected, washed with ether and alcohol and then crystallised from glacial acetic acid with a few drops of water. Prismatic needles, m.p. 301°-302°. (Found: N, 14·92, 15·05. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2N$ requires N, 14·58 per cent.).

The product is sparingly soluble in boiling water and alcohol. It readily dissolves in alkali to a colourless solution from which it is precipitated unchanged by acidulation. It also dissolves in concentrated hydrochloric or sulphuric acid and is precipitated on dilution with water. The constitution of the product was ascertained by comparing it with the quinoline derivative synthesised from hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone and cyanoacetamide by one of us (*loc. cit.*) who recorded that it does not melt even at 290°. A mixture of this and our present compound melted at 302°.

The compound was also hydrolysed with sulphuric acid (80 per cent.) when an acid melting at 266° was isolated by diluting the sulphuric acid solution. An acid m. p. (266-67°) was also obtained from Sen-gupta's quinoline derivative, and the mixture of the two melted at the same temperature.

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